

AUC: Asian Journal of Religious Studies |
66/2 Mar-Apr 2021, ISSN 2249-1503 | 22-28
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4558506
Stable URL: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558506>

Tenants of Psychological Reality: Navigating Human Unconscious

Thomas Mathew RP

Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

Abstract: Unconscious communication is the subtle, unintentional, unconscious cues that provide information to the unsettling and deeply buried layers in the human mind. While the focus of the present article is based on comparison between Freudian and Jungian studies, It's important to note that the systematic enquiry into the working of the unconscious was spearheaded by French Neurologist Jean – Martin Charcot. The unconscious can speak in multiple ways, it can be verbal (speech patterns), physical activity while speaking, or the tone of an individual or can be nonverbal such as body language and facial expressions. Many decisions are based on the unconscious communication, which is interpreted and created in the right hemisphere of the brain. The right hemisphere is dominant in perceiving and expressing body language, facial expressions, verbal cues and other indications that have to do with emotion but does not exclusively deal with the

Cite as: Mathew, Thomas (2021). Tenants of Psychological Reality: Navigating Human Unconscious (Version 1.0). AUC: Asian Journal of Religious Studies, Mar-April 2021(66/2), 22–28. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558506>

unconscious. The subject matter of unconscious has evolved dynamically over the past few centuries and the concept of mental health disorders and it's relation to the unconscious. In the light of the development of the study of the unconscious, it's worthwhile to look at some critical features and contributions by Freud and Jung.

Keywords: Collective Unconscious, Personal Unconscious, Repressed Memories, Archetypes, Psychic Energy, Psycho-pathology.

Approaching the Unconscious

Human personality is a complex one. In our day to day life we are not fully aware to what extent and how human organs are involved in our functional capacities. For example: To what extent are we aware that every minute of life, the human heart silently pumps five litres of blood to the vascular system to nourish and keep every single human cell alive? In the same way we need to understand human mind is fully operational at all times unconsciously and consciously. In our understanding of human psyche, the unconscious remains to be a mystery for human kind because it unfolds deep reservoirs in front of us. It's important for us to understand that long before Sigmund Freud or even William James the idea of unconscious was a subject matter throughout history.

Therefore, it is worthwhile to underline remarkable influence of opposing views of Sigmund Freud and Carl Jung even as we wrestle to comprehend the 'concept of evolving human psyche'. For Freud it was a sum total of repressed memories and for analytical and spiritual mind of Carl Jung (analytical psychologist) the individual unconscious is open to the collective unconscious of the archetypes, which according to the nature of his work is the collection of symbols and images. It functions as a link between the personal unconscious and the collective unconscious. "For Freud his first concept of the unconscious as being the total of repressed memories and tendencies" (Ellenberge, 1970: 146).

As the unconscious represents different levels and rich layers of human personality, we can be curious to grasp its operation. It contains emotions and memories that connect the personality of the person with the past life. Our journey through the fantasies and dreams can unfold many revelations that make the link with the present and the future. As Freud termed dreaming “the royal road to the unconscious”. According to Freud unfulfilled wishes and urges are in the unconscious. Our realm of consciousness has many gaps that prevent us from recalling our experiences from the past life. We don’t know where some of our personal ideas and assumptions come from and consciousness does not provide us any proof, this I believe should broaden our horizon to explore the unconscious. Jung coined his understanding of unconscious in three ways and they are personal unconscious, collective unconscious and consciousness. Jung’s unconscious evolved unlikely to Freudian’s concept as it connects through the archetypal images, symbols and dreams in communion with humanity.

However, we need to acknowledge Freud’s revolutionary contribution in developing arena of unconscious and bringing it forth to the systematic study of the subject. During the 19th century the dominant trend in the Western thought was positivism, i.e.; positive affirmation can come from authentic scientific knowledge and such a period of revolution subscribed to Freudian thinking. Crucial to the operation of the unconscious is ‘repression’. According to Freud, we often experience thoughts and feelings which are so painful that we cannot bear them and associated memories, Freud argued, be banished from conscious mind, the number of gaps in the conscious mind paves for the unconscious to gain an edge over human memories. An example I can think here is transference experience in therapy, (memory of the past reflecting in therapy room in a light hearted manner) something shared intentionally in therapy either by a client (patient) or by therapist becomes a

healing agent. Jung developed the unconscious in such a way to understand that unlocking the unconscious can offer deep reservoirs for our personal growth and development.

Unconscious is Dynamic

This is a process of interplay of the driving forces in the unconscious. It explores mental phenomena as the result of the interaction and counteraction of forces. A dynamic system examines the phenomena in terms of processes of development of progression or regression. These are both urging forces and checking forces, there is reciprocity between urging forces and checking forces. For example: A person's id urges him to pay injustice with injustice, like the memory of the murder of his father that happened when he was a child. Now he is of age and he wants to revenge, but his superego comes into play strongly to remind him of his need to transform his life and subsequently of the legal consequences. What is the role of Christian spirituality in this effort of transformation? How can the therapist / pastoral care giver utilize psychological resources and his faith tradition for effective intervention? How can he be present in suffering?

“External frustration is a state of privation or deprivation, while internal frustration is a state of inner inhibition” (Hall, 1976: 9).

The nucleus of the unconscious consists of instinctual representatives which seek to discharge their wishful impulses. These instinctual impulses co-ordinate with one another, exist side by side without being influenced by one another and exempt from mutual contradiction.

Therefore, it could be a primary tenet in the psychoanalytic circle the deeply painful memories inhabited in us and they are part of the psychopathology of everyday life. The psychic process does not bring into consciousness, but dealt by the mental energies in the dynamic unconscious.

The Idea of Illness

The idea of illness and cure was associated with various cultural and religious meanings. The religious leaders and clergymen assumed crucial roles in alleviating illness and pronouncing cure. There were myths and beliefs about the nature of illness and in many ways it added to the development of illness and the cure of it. There was a basic understanding that unequal distribution of energy could be the cause for the illness. It's interesting to note how persons like Mesmer viewed aetiology of illness. It could be that there is a connection between what happens in our mind-body systems and cosmos. Health and wellbeing depends upon man's inherent relationship to the environment and if there is imbalance in that connection and lack of effort to repair the imbalance can possibly lead to breakdown.

The Unconscious Can Be Accessed and Interacted with

We can access and interact with the unconscious through symbols and images. When interaction takes place with the unconscious, there is transformation of psychic energy and removal of the mental blocks result in healing. Before the emergence of modern psychiatry there were culturally bound beliefs that contributed to various methods of treatment. There were exorcists who had exercised power over what was called long discussions with the evil spirits and the spirits agreed to leave at a given time and under certain conditions. The most crucial aspect that evolved in terms of entering into the unconscious was the therapist's ability to establish rapport with patient and his resilience to continue in that rapport. There is transmission of psychic energy into patient to elicit response. The end result depends on the outcome of reciprocity of patient in response to the shared rapport between patient and therapist.

Freud believed in free association that helped him to journey with his patients into their unconscious.

The modern psychoanalytic model has evolved through trials and errors. There is no doubt that Freud made an outstanding contribution in the rediscovery and promotion of the unconscious, despite his certain dogmatic approaches to the unconscious. Jung's contribution to the subject with the expansion of collective unconscious opened the gates in such ways to look at the functioning of the unconscious from cultural and universal perspectives.

Spiritual Care and Psychoanalysis

There are fundamental differences and similarities between pastoral care and psychoanalytical work. At the outset, it should be noted that pastoral care / spiritual care is based on the confession of faith and psychoanalysis is based on the medical model. Traditionally, pastoral care-givers are expected to play a direct role in solving the problems of the people based on the faith tradition of their congregation and in line with the dogmatic approach of the biblical concepts, whereas in psychotherapy, the patient along with the therapist through therapy engages in searching the meaning of any lived past and current experience in joint venture. Personal experiences, thought process and emotional experiences of the patients/ clients accorded significance by all means in the context of caregiver's relationship with the other.

Jungian analyst involves with the tradition and any form of faith and images which patient brings into therapy. Both Psychoanalysis and Pastoral care aims to facilitate healing process. The challenge is to learn to develop resources and culturally relevant approaches to bring about the relationship and usefulness between faith traditions and modern psychological thought.. Jung offers vast resources to enhance the skills of the spiritual care givers and provide great insights in understanding the struggles of individuals in multicultural context.

We can integrate spiritual dimension into psychotherapeutic resources taking into consideration the rapidly changing socio-cultural conditions of individuals and groups. There is both conscious and unconscious search for appropriate and sensitive ‘ spirituality driven therapy to address many unfamiliar terrains of the psyche today.

Conclusion

The study of spiritual resources/religious dimensions for the benefit and wellbeing of persons in illness and suffering can be very inspiring and challenging. This area of discovery of the unconscious cannot be a comfortable journey, but a road less travelled. At the same time, there is constant drive across the cultures to search for the the meaning of life journey in the midst of chaos and breakdown. In this context, this work can add some value for those in academic circles and care givers who are engaged in healing touch, transformation of individuals and community.

Reference

Ellenberger, *The Discovery of the Unconscious*, p.146, Basic Books, 1970)

Hall, C. S. (1979). *A Primer of Freudian Psychology*. New York, NY: New American Library.

Mathew Thomas, MTh, EMDR (Australia), CPE (USA) PhD (Canada) RP (Ontario) is Licensed Psychotherapist, family therapist and addiction treatment specialist currently based in Ho Chin Minh City, Vietnam and he works as senior consultant with TeleCBT, Canada. He can be contacted at matt@riverbendcounselling.ca ORCID: 0000-0002-4592-7497.

Article Received: Feb 12, 2021, Accepted: Feb 18, 2021; No of Words: 1840

© by the authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license. (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)